

EFFECT OF NPK 15:15:15 ON PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES, NODULATION AND PLANT HEIGHT
OF *Arachis hypogea* AND *Voandzeia subterranea* USING INDIGENOUS RHIZOBIUM

Ngwu, O. E

Department of Agronomy and Ecological Management, Faculty of Agriculture and Natural Resource Management,
Enugu State University of Science and Technology, P.M.B. 01660, Enugu, Enugu State, Nigeria.

Ngwuoe@yahoo.com.

ABSTRACT

The effect of NPK 15:15:15 on nodulation, plant height, soil temperature, weed density and physicochemical properties of groundnut (*Arachis hypogea*) and bambara nut (*Voandzeia subterranean*) using indigenous rhizobium in an Ultisol were studied in 2005 planting season with a view to finding out if NPK 15:15:15 will improve or reduce nodulation at 120 kg/ha, 60 kg/ha, and 0 kg/ha the control. The design was a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications, using the Teaching and Research Farm, Faculty of Agriculture, Enugu State University of Science and Technology as experimental site. Result showed that *Voandzeia subterranea* produced highest quantities of nodules at NPK fertilizer rate of 120 kg/ha at 30 and 60 DAP followed by that with treatment at 60 kg/ha, whereas the control plot produces the least number of nodules.

The result also showed that the legume ability to nodulate was affected by the treatment at various levels, this therefore should be taken into consideration when selecting the levels of treatments to be applied in a given plot. It was also observed that plant height and nitrogen content increased at 120 kg/ha of the inorganic fertilizer.

KEYWORDS: *Soil temperature, weed density, plant height, Nodulation, A. hypogea, V. subterranea.*

INTRODUCTION

Arachis hypogea and *Voandzeia subterranea* are available every year and are cheap food energy sources. They are suitable in present farming and food system in Africa and they play major role to alleviate the food crisis. *A. hypogea* pods are rich in oil (35-50%), protein and vitamin B and C while *V. subterranea* are low in protein (16-18%), 8% fat, 65% carbohydrate, 45% ash. Unlike *Vigna unguiculata*, *A. hypogea* and *V. subterranea* not well nodulated are unable to fix nitrogen to meet plant requirements except with the addition of inorganic fertilizer (Ngwu, 2005). McDonald (1985) stated that rhizobia in the soil tend to die in absence of normal host plant especially in acid soil, he further suggested that if a crop is to be grown on new land, it is very likely to inoculate or add inorganic fertilizer to improve the productivity of the crop and for the sustainability of the land.

V. subterranea are recorded to be drought tolerant with associated Rhizobia and can survive nodulation and fix Nitrogen at high temperature, they are also promising for dry land farming. Nitrogen fixation is said to depress the percentage of legume and this reduces the protein production from that source; the main nutrient required is Phosphorus because this element is usually strongly fixed in highly weathered acid soil (Olsen and Moe 1980).

The NPK fertilizer at ratio of 15:15:15 provides the soil with equal amount of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium and this will enable us to evaluate equal application of nutrient and their functions to *A. hypogea*

and *V. subterranea*. The inorganic fertilizer may influence the adaptation, persistence, ability to dominate and flourish best in legume production.

The experiment was carried out at the Teaching and Research Farm of the Faculty of Agriculture, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu, Nigeria. The area is characterized by humid tropical climate with wet season between (April-October) and dry season between (November-March). The annual rainfall of the area is between 1700mm to 1800mm. Two crops were used for the study namely: Groundnut (*Arachis hypogea*) and Bambara groundnut (*Voandzeia subterranea*).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experimental area was mowed and trashes removed before the land was ploughed and harrowed prior to planting. A total land area of 7 m x 14.5 m was used for the experiment. The area was cultivated into 18 sub plots of 2 m x 2 m each with 0.5 m alley in between the plots. Soil samples were collected from each sub plot using soil auger and poly bags at 30, 60 and 90 days after planting. The composite samples were collected randomly from each sub plots before planting. Later the samples were subjected to laboratory analysis.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three treatments replicated three times. The treatments are N₁₅P₁₅K₁₅ at 36 g, 72 g and control (block without NPK). The treatments were randomly applied in each sub plots. The field layout is as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Field Layout and Treatment Combinations

Key:

- g - Groundnut
- BG - Bambara Groundnut
- Og - No treatment applied
- 36g - 36 grams of NPK
- 72g - 72 grams of NPK

The crops were planted with spacing 45 cm x 45 cm at the rate of two seeds per hole. Seeds that did not germinate after one week were supplied one week after planting and some were thinned down to one plant

per hole two weeks after planting. Fertilizer was added a month after planting. Weeding was done during the period of the experiment manually with the aid of hoe every three weeks intervals for four times.

The physicochemical analysis of soil samples were carried out as follows: The nitrate nitrogen of the soil was determined using Brucine calorimetric method. The pH of the soil was determined in distilled water using a soil/liquid ratio of 1:2.5 using a Beckman pH meter. The complexometric titration method described by Chapman (1982) was used for determination of calcium, magnesium, sodium and potassium were determined from I N ammonium acetate (NH₄OAC) using the flame photometer. Exchangeable acidity was determined by titrimetric method using I N KCl extract (Mclean, 1982). Soil temperature was determined using earth thermometer which was inserted into a hole dug 5cm depth to take the readings.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Physicochemical properties of *A. hypogea* and *V. subterranea* plot with different levels of treatment at 30, 60 and 90 DAP. Table (1) shows the differences in nitrate nitrogen composition at different time scale. At 90 DAP observation made showed that NO₃-N (nitrate nitrogen) composition of the soil for plot with *V. Subterranea* and *A. hypogea* with NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha (2.3 and 2.2 mg/kg) when compared to plots with NPK 15:15:15 at 60 kg/ha by 4.3.5 and 45.5% respectively. The control plot with both crop was observed to be reducing by 5.8 and 13.1% when compared with plots of both crops at 60 kg/ha. This result got may be due to the fact that NPK fertilizer helps to increase the availability of Nitrate Nitrogen for easy absorption by crop. At 30 DAP it was observed that plot with 60 kg/ha was found to contain high nitrate nitrogen (0.12 mg/kg) when compared to plot of the same crop with NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha (0.1 mg/kg) by 8.3% higher.

The control plot of *A. hypogea* shows lowest content of nitrate nitrogen. This result may be due to the fact that NPK 15:15:15 at 60 kg/ha had been absorbed by the soil colloidal particles resulting in the inability for crop to utilize fertilizer whereas plots containing NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha had been absorbed by soil colloidal particle and some are still .5 available in the soil, in order for crop to utilize. This leads to reduction in the amount of available nitrate nitrogen. At 60 DAP the control plot of *V. subterranea* contains the lowest NO₃-N when compared with plot containing NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha and at 60 kg/ha by 93.8 and 96.4% lower. Also in the control plot with *A. hypogea* at 60 DAP it was observed that it contains the lowest NO₃-N when compared with plots containing NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha and at 60 kg/ha by 94.6 and 97% lower. Minchin and Jonas (1986) characterized soil containing NPK fertilizer at different rates and showed that fertilizer is absorbed by soil colloidal particle, leading to increase in nitrate nitrogen when the rate of applied fertilizer is not in excess.

Results also showed that plot of *A. hypogea* with NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha has the highest content of Ca (3.4 Cmol⁽⁺⁾kg⁻¹) and this meant 6.8% more Ca than that plot containing no treatment (3.17 Cmol⁽⁺⁾kg⁻¹) at 30 DAP, it also had 2.9% more Ca than that plot containing NPK 15:15:15 at 60 kg/ha (3.30 Cmol⁽⁺⁾kg⁻¹). Also at 30 DAP plots containing *V. subterranea* with NPK 15:15:15 120 kg/ha showed the lowest content of Ca (table 1) with (3.1 Cmol⁽⁺⁾kg⁻¹). This meant 11.4% less Ca than the plot containing no treatment (3.53 Cmol⁽⁺⁾kg⁻¹) which showed the highest Ca content with NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha (2.93 Cmol⁽⁺⁾kg⁻¹) followed by plots with treatment at 60 kg/ha (3.4 Cmol⁽⁺⁾kg⁻¹).

At 30 DAP, the result showed that plot with *A. hypogea*, without treatment (control plot) had the highest Mg content (2.6 Cmol⁽⁺⁾kg⁻¹) when compared to *A. hypogea* plot with treatment having the lowest Mg content by 33%. Plots with *V. subterranea* was observed to have the highest Mg with treatment at 120 kg/ha (2.15 Cmol⁽⁺⁾kg⁻¹). At 90 DAP, *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* plot without treatment (control plot) had the lowest Mg content. The result also showed that the content of Na is highest in plots of *A. hypogea* and *V. subterranea* with NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha and 60 kg/ha (0.073) and (0.072 Cmol⁽⁺⁾kg⁻¹) respectively when compared with plots without treatment with *A. hypogea* and *V. subterranea* (0.07 and 0.07 Cmol⁽⁺⁾kg⁻¹) by 4.1 and 2.9% higher at 30 DAP, while at 60 DAP Na content was found to reduce with plots of *A. hypogea* and *V. subterranea* without treatment from 60 DAP and 90 DAP.

It was also shown that Potassium content in plot of *A. hypogea* and *V. subterranea* with NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha were higher (0.8 and 0.6 $\text{Cmol}^{(+)}\text{kg}^{-1}$) than those with 60 kg/ha (0.6 and 0.5 $\text{Cmol}^{(+)}\text{kg}^{-1}$) by 13.8 and 13.7%. It was also observed that K content in each plot was reduced from 60 to 90 DAP. This may be as a result of nutrient uptake by both leguminous crops. The result obtained from exchangeable acidity shows that Al content in plot of *A. hypogea* containing NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha and 60 kg/ha were high (0.52 and 0.43 $\text{Cmol}^{(+)}\text{kg}^{-1}$) than those that are in the control plot by 53.2 and 26.8%. Also plots of *V. subterranea* containing NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha had the highest Al content followed by plot containing NPK 15:15:15 at 60 kg/ha and then the control plot with the lowest Al. It was also observed that Al content was reduced from 60 DAP to 90 DAP, this is may be as a result of absorption of NPK fertilizer in the soil colloidal particle.

Table 1: Physicochemical Properties of *A. hypogea* and *V. subterranean* Plot with Different Levels of Treatments at 30, 60 and DAP

Sample description	NO ₃ -N (mgkg ⁻¹)			pH			Exchangeable Bases (Cmol ⁽⁺⁾ kg ⁻¹)									Exch. Acidity Cmol ⁽⁺⁾ kg ⁻¹ Al					
	30 DAP	60 DAP	90 DAP	30 DAP	60 DAP	90 DAP	Ca			Mg			Na			P			30 DAP	60 DAP	90 DAP
A. hypogea (Control 0kg/ha)	0.09	0.07	0.04	5.64	5.26	2.2	3.17	3.08	2.8	2.06	1.58	1.2	0.07	0.05	0.0	0.69	0.51	0.4	0.52	0.47	0.48
A. hypogea (60kg/ha)	0.12	2.30	1.22	5.32	5.21	5.1	3.30	3.18	3.0	1.33	2.07	1.7	0.72	0.70	0.5	0.075	0.62	0.5	0.43	0.40	0.43
A hypogea (120kg/ha)	0.11	1.25	2.30	5.70	5.27	5.24	3.40	3.35	2.95	1.38	1.35	1.01	0.073	0.71	0.6	0.80	0.71	0.68	0.52	0.41	0.38
V. Subterranea (0kg/ha)	0.11	0.08	0.05	5.40	5.23	5.19	3.53	3.43	3.20	1.73	1.67	1.43	0.070	0.03	0.0	0.50	0.10	0.09	0.37	0.45	0.52
V. Subterranea (60kg/ha)	0.09	2.23	1.27	5.97	5.50	5.40	3.50	3.4	3.15	1.84	1.67	1.46	0.071	0.07	0.6	0.53	0.15	0.10	0.04	0.51	0.53
V. Subterranea (120kg/ha)	0.10	1.29	1.29	5.32	5.70	5.14	3.10	2.93	2.60	1.15	1.69	1.49	0.072	0.78	0.7	0.58	0.47	0.38	0.49	0.44	0.42

The Effect of NPK 15:15:15 on Nodulation of *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* at 30, 60 and 90 DAP is as shown in (Table 2).

Result shows that fertilizer application at various rates affected nodulation at 30 and 60 DAP (Table 2). It was observed that *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* with NPK 15:15:15 treatment at 120 kg/ha produced significantly ($P < 0.05$) the highest quantity of nodules with 4.19 and 30.5 respectively at 30 DAP. NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha, that was applied to *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* had between 17.4 and 0.98% more nodule than those with NPK 15:15:15 at 60kg/ha. Both crops on the control plot (no treatment) produced the lowest number of nodules for *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* when compared with *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* at 60 kg/ha and these were respectively 3.3 and 16.5% significantly higher at 30 DAP.

At 60 DAP it was observed that the nodules produced per plant reduced drastically in both crops treated with NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha. This may be due to the effect of weed on the crops and also the effect of high temperature. According to Panthurst and Sprent (1996) the greatest number of nodule per root and percentage of root nodulated were formed at 25°C and a drastic decline occurs when the temperature rises above 30°C.

Also at 60 DAP it was observed that *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* with treatment at 120 kg/ha nodulated more when compared with both crops in plot containing 60kg/ha and the control plot by 528 and 33.2% for *A. hypogea*

and 36.7 and 24.5% for *V. subterranea*. *V. subterranea* was observed to produce more nodule than *A. hypogea*. This result is also in confirmation with that got Abaido (1990) who found that application of NPK fertilizer increased nodule mass and observation in the field further showed that there was nodule decay at 90 DAP.

Table 2: Number of Nodules Produced by *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* at 30 and 60 DAP.

Variety/treatment	Days after planting	
	30	60
A. hypogea (control)	29.2	9.0
A. hypogea (60kg/ha)	30.2	9.2
A hypogea (120kg/ha)	30.5	14.5
V. substerranea (Control)	28.9	10.6
V. substerranea (60kg/ha)	34.6	13.5
V. substerranea (120kg/ha)	41.9	18.8
FLSD - 0.05	13.2	3.21

Effect of NPK 15:15:15 on plant height as in (Table 3).

The result showed that fertilizer application at various rates affected plant height (Table 3). *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* with NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha had the highest ($P<0.05$) plant height with 20.2 cm and 23.7 cm respectively. These were significantly higher ($P<0.05$) than the plant height of *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* with NPK 15:15:15 at 60 kg/ha by 17 and 3.5%. These result indicated that NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha was not in excess, it was fully utilized by the plants for maximum growth.

At 60 DAP the control plot (No treatment) of *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* had the lowest plant height of 26.6 cm and 24.2 cm respectively, when compared to *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* with NPK 15:15:15 at 60 kg/ha with 16.1 and 15.2% significantly higher. Control plot of *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* which had the lowest ($P<0.05$) plant height at 30 DAP and 60 DAP, however had the lowest plant height at 90 DAP with 31.8 and 29.3 respectively (Table 3). This is because NPK 15:15:15 was applied, to boost up the crops growth rate. Plant height of *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* with NPK 15:15:15 at 60 kg/ha was followed by that of the control plot with 35.2 cm and 32.5 cm respectively. The results showed that both crops in soil treated with NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha showed increase in plant height from 30 DAP to 90 DAP indicating that soil treated with NPK 15:15:15 at 60 kg/ha, was not available for plant absorption due to the fact that some of the fertilizer was held by soil colloidal particle. This result is in confirmation with (Russel and Johnston 1980) who stated that when fertilizer and organic manure are applied to soil they only show their effects on plant growth and productivity when they are in adequate supply.

Effect of Soil temperature on the production of *A. hypogea* and *V. subterranea* at 30, 60 and 90 DAP (Table 4). It was observed that soil temperature affected *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* at 30, 60 and 90 DAP (Table 4).

Observation showed that the entire production of both crops were affected significantly ($P<0.05$). The average temperature from 30 to 90 DAP was 36.0°C, this shows why nodulation reduced drastically at 60 DAP. The yield was also affected. This result is in conformity with that got by Pankhurst and Sprent (1996) who found that the greatest number of nodules per root and percentage root nodulated at 25°C were high and that a drastic decline occurs when temperature rises above 30°C.

Table 3: Plant height of *A. hypogea* and *V. subterranea* at 30, to and 90 DAP.

Variety/treatment	Days after planting		
	30	60	90
A. hypogea (control)	18.6cm	24.2cm	29.3cm
A. hypogea (60kg/ha)	19.5cm	28.5cm	32.5cm
A hypogea (120kg/ha)	20.2cm	34.6cm	38.2cm
V. subterranea (Control)	21.9cm	26.6cm	31.8cm
V. subterranea (60kg/ha)	23.3cm	31.7cm	35.2cm
V. subterranea (120kg/ha)	23.7cm	39.6cm	42.7cm
FLSD - 0.05	3.56	6.89	4.87

Table 4: Soil Temperature of *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* at 30, 60 and 90 DAP.

Variety/treatment	Temperature (°C)		
	30	60	90
A. hypogea (control)	32.3	34.2	33.5
A. hypogea (60kg/ha)	33.8	32.0	34.5
A hypogea (120kg/ha)	32.3	34.5	32.0
V. subterranea (Control)	34.0	35.5	34.0
V. subterranea (60kg/ha)	33.0	33.1	33.0
V. subterranea (120kg/ha)	33.0	33.0	34.1
FLSD - 0.05	3.00	3.10	2.98

Effect of weed density on production of *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* at 30 DAP as shown in (Table 5).

Result showed that fertilizer application helps to speed up weed growth which affected significantly *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* production.

It was observed that weed density increased in plot with NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha and reduced in plot without treatment. Weed density of (6.3 and 9.3) were observed in plots of *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* with 120 kg/ha respectively, whereas weed density of both crop in plots without treatment showed 4.7 and 3.2 respectively (Table 5); this meant 25.4 and 65.6% significantly lower at 30 DAP. This result is in confirmation with that got by Holl (1995) who reported, that weed density on any plot of land has a great effect in reducing productivity of the crop in that plot.

CONCLUSION

From the results it was found out that *V. subterranea* and *A. hypogea* have different characteristics at different time scale. It was comparatively observed that *V. subterranea* made use of NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha to produce more number of nodules than *A. hypogea*; hence *V. subterranea* should be chosen when Nitrogen fixation in the soil is to be considered. The physicochemical property of the soil showed that plots that contain NPK 15:15:15 at 120 kg/ha showed the highest nitrate nitrogen content followed by the plot with NPK 15:15:15 at 60 kg/ha with the plot containing no treatment (control plot) having the lowest Nitrate Nitrogen, hence, treatment at 120 kg/ha should be taken as the correct treatment to be applied in this circumstance because in as much as some of the fertilizer, are being absorbed by soil colloidal particle, substantial amount was available for crop uptake. Result also showed that the overall grading of both legumes studied indicated that *V. subterranea* had the highest plant height measurement and that high temperature and weed density affect nodulation and plant growth.

Table 5: Weed density on production of *V. subterranea* and *A. Hypogea* at 30 DAP.

Variety/treatment	Weed density (g)
A. hypogea (control)	3.2
A. hypogea (60kg/ha)	5.3
A hypogea (120kg/ha)	6.3
V. substerranea (Control)	4.7
V. substerranea (60kg/ha)	7.3
V. substerranea (120kg/ha)	9.3
FLSD - 0.05	3.4

REFERENCES

- Abaido, N. K. (1990). Application of NPK Fertilizer and its Effect on Nodulation. *J. Exp. Agric.* 24, 120-128.
- Bremner, J. M. and Malvaney, C. S. (2007). Nitrogen Total In Page et al (eds.). *Methods of Soil Analysis, Part 2.* ASA No. 9, Madison, Wisconsin, pp. 595-625.
- Chapman, H. D. (1982). Total Exchangeable Bases In C. A. Black (ed): *Method of Soil Analysis Part II.* ASA, 9, pp. 902-904, Madison, Wisconsin.
- Holl, D. J. (1995). Interactions Between Varieties and Nutrition in Nodulation and Symbiosis of Soyabeans. *Pesq. Agropec. Bras.* 2, 475-487.
- McDonald, N. T. (1985). Fertilizer Trial with *V. Subterrenea* and *V. Sinensis* on Arentto Botucates Soil With a Shrub Savannah Vegetation. *Bragantis*, 23, 45-54.
- McLean, E. O. (1982). Soil pH and lime. Requirements in Taga A. L. (Ed). *Method of Soil Analysis Part 2. Chemical and Microbial Properties (2nd Edition).* Agronomy Series No. 9.
- Minchin N. J., Jonas, E. F. (1986). Soil Fertility, Legumes and Rhizobium Efficiency. Part I: Introduction, Effect of Organic Matter and Soil Reaction. *Agric. Digest*; 19, 3.
- Ngwu, O. E. (2005). Comparative Studies of Nitrogen Fixing Potential of *Desmodium Ramississimon* and *Vigna Unquiculata* for Soil Fertility Management. *Tropicultura*, 23(2), 110-116.
- Olsen, E. T. and Moe, L. O. (1980). Root Nodule Symbiosis and Tropical Grain Legume Production. In *Proceedings First IITA Grain Legume Improvement Workshop*, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Pankhurst, S. T. and Sprent, G. T. (1996). The Nodulation of Legumes in Madagascar *Agron. Trop.* 8, 120-125.
- Russel, I. J., Johnston, E. D. (1980). The Influence of Nutritional Nitrogen. Fixation and Growth of Legume. In *A Review of Nitrogen in the Tropics with Particular Reference to Human Consumption.* Bul. 116, pp. 130-146.

Received for Publication: 10/08/2007

Accepted for Publication: 20/10/2007